

DHYANA AND PARADHYANA

Introduction

In the realm of the mind and its intricate workings, the concepts of *Dhyana* (Meditation) and *Paradhyana* (Distraction) offer profound insight into the human experience of focus and consciousness. Meditation, or Dhyana, is a process of centering the mind, while Paradhyana represents the opposite—a state of distraction where the mind drifts into irrelevant thoughts. This journal explores these two Dhyanas, offering a classification, analysis, and associated formulas for both.

Dhyana(Meditation)

Dhyana is the practice of focusing the mind, a vital part of mental discipline in various spiritual traditions. Meditation allows the mind to either remain still or to concentrate on the present moment.

1. Mind Focused on Stillness

In this form of Dhyana, the goal is to bring the mind to complete stillness, removing all distractions. The practitioner moves beyond the fluctuations of thought, emotion, and sensory input, achieving a state of mental quietness.

Formula for Stillness Meditation:

Let:

- M = Mind's activity
- S = Stillness of mind
- T = Thought processes

$$M = \lim_{T \rightarrow 0} S$$

As the thoughts (T) approach zero, the mind's activity reaches a state of complete stillness (S). In this state, the mind becomes unperturbed by external stimuli, allowing a deeper connection with one's inner self.

Mind Focused on Stillness (Standard)

Objective: To measure and achieve a state of mental stillness by minimizing thought activity.

Formula:

$$M_s = \lim_{T \rightarrow 0} S$$

Where:

- M_s = Meditation in stillness (standard value)
- T = Thought processes (number of thoughts per minute)
- S = Stillness (measured as the absence of mental fluctuations)

Standard Range:

- M_s is achieved when $T \approx 0$ and $S \geq 95\%$ (mental quietness). Stillness is defined as a mind free from thoughts and external sensory distractions for at least 5 minutes during meditation practice.

2. Mind Focused on the Present

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Formula for Present-focused Meditation:

Let:

- M = Mind's focus
- P = Present moment
- D = Degree of distraction

$$M = \frac{P}{D}$$

As the degree of distraction (D) decreases, the mind's focus on the present (P) becomes stronger, leading to an immersive meditative state.

Mind Focused on the Present (Standard)

Objective: To measure the degree of focus on the present moment, considering external distractions.

Formula:

$$M_p = \frac{P}{D}$$

Where:

- M_p = Meditation in the present moment (standard value)
- P = Present moment awareness (measured on a scale of 0 to 100%)
- D = Degree of distraction (measured as interruptions per minute)

Standard Range:

- $M_p \geq 90\%$ is considered the international standard for present-focused meditation. This requires present-moment awareness (P) to be 90% or higher, with distractions (D) limited to less than 5% of the meditation period.

Paradhyana(Distraction)

Paradhyana occurs when the mind deviates from its intended focus, wandering into irrelevant or unnecessary thought patterns. There are two key types of *Paradhyana*.

1. Mind Focused on the Past or Future

In this form of *Paradhyana*, the mind oscillates between past experiences or future anticipations, detaching from the present. Such distractions hinder productivity, focus, and emotional balance.

Formula for Distraction by Time:

Let:

- F_p = Focus on past
- F_f = Focus on future
- P_m = Present moment focus
- T = Time

$$P_m = \frac{1}{F_p + F_f}$$

As the mind's focus on the past (F_p) and future (F_f) increases, the ability to remain in the present moment (P_m) diminishes.

Mind Focused on the Past or Future (Standard)

Objective: To quantify the mind's deviation from the present due to thoughts about the past or future.

Formula:

$$P_m = \frac{1}{F_p + F_f}$$

Where:

- P_m = Present-moment focus (in inverse relation to past and future focus)
- F_p = Focus on past (measured as the percentage of time spent on past-related thoughts)
- F_f = Focus on future (measured as the percentage of time spent on future-related thoughts)

Standard Range:

- A value of $P_m \geq 80\%$ is the standard, indicating that no more than 20% of the mind's attention is on the past or future during a mental focus period.

2. Mind Focused on the Sleeping Mode

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Formula for Sleep Distraction:

Let:

- S_m = Sleep mode distraction
- C = Conscious awareness
- M = Mental focus

$$S_m = \frac{C}{M}$$

As mental focus (M) decreases, the mind drifts into sleep mode, and conscious awareness (C) declines, leading to a state of disconnection from reality.

2.2 Mind Focused on the Sleeping Mode (Standard)

Objective: To measure the degree of distraction caused by the mind slipping into a sleeping mode or lethargy.

Formula:

$$S_m = \frac{C}{M}$$

Where:

- S_m = Sleep mode distraction (standard value)
- C = Conscious awareness (measured as a percentage of time being fully aware)
- M = Mental focus (measured by the level of sustained attention)

Standard Range:

- $S_m \leq 20\%$ is considered the international standard for meditation focus. A higher S_m value suggests excessive distraction and drowsiness, whereas maintaining at least 80% conscious awareness (C) ensures proper mental engagement during meditation.

Mental Focus Calculation (General Formula):

$$M_f = \frac{F_{\text{total}}}{D + S}$$

Where:

- M_f = Mental focus (general value)
- F_{total} = Total focus time (measured as the period of concentration)
- D = Degree of distraction (distractions per minute)
- S = Sleep mode or lethargy (measured as time spent in an unfocused or sleepy state)

International Standard:

- $M_f \geq 85\%$ of the session must be focused, with distractions and lethargy contributing to no more than 15% of total meditation time.

Conclusion

Both Dhyana and Paradyana represent different Dhyanas of mental engagement. While meditation encourages mental clarity and presence, distraction scatters the mind and inhibits productivity. Understanding these mental Dhyanas, their types, and their associated formulas allows individuals to better manage their mental energy and maintain focus in a world full of distractions.

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